

Barriers of Using the Flipped Classroom Strategy, from the Standpoint of Science Teachers in Jordan

Shaimaa' Mkhymryahya, Mohammad Nayef Ayasrah, Mohareb Ali Alsmadi,
Shorouq Mansour al-etan

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Barriers, Flipped, Classroomstrategy, Science Teachers</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5369606</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to detect the barriers of using flipped classroom strategy, from the standpoint of science teachers in Jordan and identified three barriers: teachers, students, and the administrative and technological factors, where the study society consists of science teachers at Amman, Irbid, and Karak governorates for the year 2020/2021. Study results showed that second field; students was the barrier agreed on by study sample as well as the existence of statistical significant differences in these barriers that attributed to males and governorates, but showed nonexistence of statistically significant differences due to teaching experience. The study made a range of recommendations, in light of its findings such as the need to conduct training workshops on the flipped class strategy and to prepare supported videos by groups of teachers to allow its use in several schools.</i></p>

Introduction

The waste of learning time during traditional classes, which represented in the transfer of scientific content from teacher to learner by relying directly on the student's book considers; to some extent an obstacle to self-learning, gaining practical experiences, and developing the thinking skills. (Al-Kuhaili, 2015) confirms that traditional processes related to the transfer of basic knowledge inside the classroom take at least (30) minutes, or (66%) of class time, where the class time in Jordan's education system for basic stage limited to (45) minutes which hinders the design of projects, the promotion of quality learning, the enablement of learners to build their own knowledge, and helping them to produce ideas and knowledge.

In order to make the best use of class time and invest in optimally, the various educational systems sought to develop the educational process and advise teachers to build modern teaching plans and strategies that will effectively invest energies of learners and integrate them effectively in the educational and learning processes, because they are effective, active, and capable of taking responsibility for their learning (Al-Madan, 2015; Milheim, 2006 & Seaman, 2005). The technical and technological development and communication systems played a major role in activating the role of learners in the learning process and gaining part of basic knowledge before they enter to class (Al-Izboon, 2020).

The increased use of Internet, especially social media sites, e-mail, and any other methods has contributed to make users continuously communicating with the Internet (Sprenger, 2010), which help teachers and learners to communicate through short videos, profiles, and images (Boettcher & Conrad, 2010), and contributed directly and indirectly to the development and discovery of new forms of learning, such as distance learning, integrated learning, and the flipped classroom (Al-Shorman, 2015). The current study is concerned with the flipped classrooms strategy, which depend on the idea of using internet technology to benefit from learning in the teacher's classrooms, in order for teachers to invest the class time in interacting with students, instead of the indoctrination and traditional lectures that used to send videos to learners before the class time (Bergmann & Sames, 2008). Learning using the flipped classrooms strategy combines the advantages of e-learning, such as using several types of multimedia, hypermedia, and the direct or indirect distance learning, and the advantages of direct traditional education that cannot be performed by e-learning (Shorman, 2015).

(Ball, 2013) sees the flipped classroom strategy to be one of the best teaching strategies that has been concerned with the adaptation of modern technologies and its integration with the direct face-to-face education. It's a type of integrated education that mixes between the traditional methods and e-learning, in a way appropriate with the requirements and needs of learners in our time and comes in agreement with the views of (Al-Madan, 2015; Milheim, 2006 & Seaman, 2005). The flipped classroom strategy also relies on the active learning (Raja, 2013) which influenced by the structural theoretical ideas that confirm learners to be an active human being capable of building knowledge and responsible for learning it, where learners believe that knowledge and good learning

occur through the integration of learners with real tasks, activities, and experiences (Hamdan, McKnight, McKnight & Arfstrom, 2013).

The flipped classroom strategy considers one of the modern technical solutions that avoid the weaknesses in traditional learning, such as the waste of time in handling past experiences and the presentation of simple conceptual content, where class time will be invested in the implementation of activities that aimed to develop the self-regulated thinking and learning skills among learners (Al-Talafha, 2020) and offer a unique combination of two education strategies (e-learning & traditional education) that were perceived as incompatible (Bishop, 2013). (Green, 2015; Butt, 2014; Halili & Zainuddin, 2016; Alamry, 2017; Bergmann & Sams, 2012) indicates that this strategy offers many benefits to students, such as flexibility of education, stirring up motivation and thinking, participation, classroom interaction, self-learning, increased achievement, and directing students to best performance while (Bruder, 2012) points out that flipped or inverse learning provides an opportunity for student-led discussions, collaborative learning, task performance, problem solving, and knowledge exploration. (Akwarshadeh, 2017 & Abdul Wahid, 2015) mentioned some advantages of flipped classroom strategies for both teachers and students, such as the use of technology in education, time investment in teaching, attracting students' attention, and the easiness of students' access to lessons by storing them on one of the websites and returning to it at the right time and place, which reduces the individual differences between students.

Whenever teachers use flipped classroom and learning strategy, they prepare lessons by building or selecting videos, audio files, or any other media associated with the cognitive content and the learning goals associated with remembering, understanding level, and absorption which will be sent to learners well before class time in order for them to see it at home or anywhere else using their smartphones, personal computers, or laptops while class time will be devoted to the discussions and development of higher thinking skills, such as analysis, installation, and evaluation (Halil & Zainuddin, 2016). Multimedia considers an essential element in this pattern, and usually the duration for viewing these media is (5-10) minutes and will be shared with learners through social media or a website for the purpose of investing class time directly in the implementation of qualitative activities, where teachers evaluate students' level at the beginning of class and then design activities inside the class to clarify concepts previously seen by learners, preserve their knowledge, and help them gain skills, and then teachers oversee the implementation of classroom activities and provide the appropriate support to those who stumble, and gradually withdraw the support provided to them (Erieboce, 2013; Brame, 2013; Herreid, 2013 & Al-Zain, 2015). The use of flipped classroom learning strategy faces some barriers, obstacles, and challenges, where some of it related to teachers and some others related to students (Abanmi, 2016), and it's possible to summarize these challenges as follows:

- Pupils do not attend classes.
- Parents don't have interest in following up on their children.
- Unavailability of technical tools and requirements.
- The occurrence of technical errors such as unavailability of internet or its continuous interruption.
- Lack of planning and good preparation of lessons by teachers before the class time.
- Teachers do not have enough time due to increased teaching quorum (Abdul Lateef, 2016).

1. PREVIOUS STUDIES

Researchers reviewed studies related to the study topic and found that studies addressed the strategy of flipped classroom from several fields, where a series of studies dealt with the relationship between this strategy and the educational achievement of students (Marlowe, 2012; Abu Hadroos & Al-Farra, 2011; Al-Abbery, 2015; Al-Ghamedi & Al-Atawi, 2018), while other studies have tried to examine the impact of flipped classroom strategy on students' motivation toward learning (Al-Izboon, 2020; Al-Ebikan & Al-Hanaki, 2016; Tuzumet, al., 2009; Alrfouh, al., 2004). Some studies have been conducted on the trends of teachers or students toward the use of flipped classroom strategy, where the study of (Johson, 2012) sought to identify trends of secondary school students in three British schools toward the flipped classroom strategy by following a quantitative and qualitative analysis method, and results showed that students have positive attitudes toward this strategy as well as their enjoyment in it.

The study of (Abu Megnim, 2014) aimed to identify trends of (80) male and female middle school teachers in Saudi Arabia toward the use of flipped classroom strategy and their training need to use it, and prepared two questionnaires as the study instruments to achieve the study purpose. Results concluded that trends of teachers and their training needs for the flipped classroom strategy were significant and study recommended the need to train teachers and invest in their positive trends. (Khalil, 2015) conducted a study that aimed to identify the impact of using flipped classroom strategy on the trends of (18) sixth graders in one school toward mathematics, and to achieve the study purpose researcher compared between two groups; one experimental and the other controlled, and results showed a positive impact of the strategy on students' trends toward mathematics in favor of the experimental group. The study of (Adedoja, 2016) aimed to reveal the trends of (237) student teachers at the Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan in Nigeria toward the flipped classroom strategy, and obstacles

they face by implementing it using the analytical descriptive approach. The study showed that study sample had positive trends toward the use of this strategy because it enabled them to interact with teachers, school content, and with each other, while the most obstacles were the poor internet connectivity and the high prices for internet subscription services.

(Attaran&Zainuddin, 2016) also conducted a descriptive study that aimed to reveal the views of one Malaysian university students toward the use of flipped classroom strategy in language education by conducting interviews with a sample of students, and study results showed that most students have positive views toward this strategy. (Ahmed, Sultan &Shaheen, 2017) conducted a study that aimed to reveal trends of high school teachers in Syria toward using the flipped classroom strategy in teaching science. Researchers used the descriptive approach and developed a questionnaire as the study tool and distributed it on a sample of (87) high school teachers, where results showed that teachers have positive attitudes toward the use of flipped classroom strategy in teaching science. The study of (Al-Laheibi&Rayyes, 2019) aimed to identify faculty members' trends in the Saudi universities toward the use of flipped learning and its implementation obstacles using the descriptive approach. The study sample consisted of (220) faculty members in the faculties of education at a number of Saudi universities using a questionnaire distributed on them and the study results showed that they have very positive trends. Results showed several obstacles that prevent the use of flipped learning in teaching, such as the difficulty of preparing videos and considering it to be a burden added to their burdens. Results also showed a nonexistence of significant differences in the faculty trends toward the use of strategy and its implementation obstacles in teaching due to gender, educational rank, and years of experience variables. Finally, the study of Abbas(2020) aimed to reveal the trends of (60) faculty members at one of the Egyptian university toward the use of flipped classroom and their training needs for it, using a questionnaire prepared for the study purpose. Study showed that trends were highly positive and there was a great need for training on the strategy at the study sample as well.

Explanation of Previous Studies:

It noticed through reviewing the previous studies, the following:

- Researchers of different countries and each according to their study are aware of the importance of flipped classroom strategy.
- Studies addressed the impact of flipped classroom strategy on the achievement and motivation of students in different subjects, such as mathematics, social sciences, and science for various levels of study (Marlowe, 2012; Abu Hadros& Al-Farra, 2011; Al-Abeery, 2015; Al-Ghamedi& Al-Atawi, 2018), while another study tried to see the impact of flipped classroom strategy on students' motivation toward learning (Al-Izboon, 2020; Al-Ebikan&Al-Hanaki, 2016; Tuzumet, al., 2009; Alrfouh, al., 2004).
- The studies used questionnaire as a good tool for obtaining different kinds of data.
- Many studies agree on the importance of student trends; (Adedoja, 2016; Attaran&Zainuddin, 2016; Johson, 2012) and teachers trends (Abbas, 2020; Ahmed, Sultan &Shaheen, 2017) toward this strategy.
- The study of (Al-Laheibi&Rayyes, 2019) indicates the existence of obstacles or barriers in using this strategy.

By reviewing the above studies, researchers find that current study agree with the previous studies; in its topic which represented in the strategy of flipped classroom and in the use of questionnaire as a tool for collecting data, and it also comes in harmony with it in emphasizing the importance of this strategy. The study came to keep up with the educational researches in the world around it, and up to researchers' knowledge it is the first Jordanian study that tried to identify the obstacles of implementing this strategy from the standpoint of Jordanian teachers in the capital of Amman, North governorate of Irbid, and South governorate of Karak; for all science branches.

3. STUDY PROBLEMS & QUESTIONS

As a response to the invitation of educational specialists that calls for the necessity to activate the students-centered teaching strategies, students will build their knowledge in an atmosphere of pleasure and suspense, and as a reply for the necessity to include modern technological methods in these strategies, the study problem represented in the obstacles that face the use of flipped classroom strategy, which considers one of the best teaching strategies that is no longer a choice for teachers and students when they want, but has become a compulsory decision due to a pandemic that has roared the world and imposed on it a complete change in the followed teaching methods, by answering two key questions:

First Question: What are the barriers of using flipped classroom strategy from teachers' standpoint?

Second Question: Are there statistically significant differences in the barriers of using flipped classroom strategy, due to the difference in governorate, gender, educational Courses, and years of experience?

4. STUDY IMPORTANCE

The importance of study shows in its attempt to identify the barriers of flipped classroom strategy, which may be the best form for returning to the educational process; in its new form that won't be the same like it was two years ago by examining opinions of a group capable of doing just that represented in male and female teachers,

the course they teach, their teaching experience, and their teaching governorate. This study, up to researchers' knowledge is one of the first local studies that address this issue and may contribute to the diagnosis of barriers, in order for those concerned people in the Ministry of Education to work on promoting everything that contributes to the development of educational process and work to overcome its barriers.

5. METHODS

5.1 Procedural Definitions:

Barriers: there is no conventional definition that explains the meaning of barriers or obstacles, and by returning to the linguistic we find inhibitors or disincentives as meanings of it, therefore it's possible to say that barriers of teachers' uses are disincentives that prevent them from using the teaching strategy of flipped classroom and distract them from the optimal use of it (Ibn Mandour, 1414). Its problems that face individuals and prevent them the benefit of any development (Mullah, 2007), and procedurally researchers develop three types of barriers: teachers, students, and administrative and technological factors.

Flipped Classroom Strategy: (Zaban, 2015:6) defined it as a teaching strategy that centered around students instead of teachers, where students watch educational videos using visual and audio techniques, virtual simulation programs, TV stories, and work papers in their homes before class time and the teacher exploits class time in providing an active and interactive learning environment, where students will be directed to implement whatever they have learned.

5.2 Study Limitations

Human Boundaries: the study was limited to science teachers in Jordan schools.

Spatial Boundaries: the study was limited to three governorates; Amman, Irbid, and Karak.

Temporal Boundaries: the study was conducted in second term of school year (2020/2021).

Topic Boundaries: the study was limited to barriers of using flipped classroom strategy by science teachers.

5.3 Study Approach

Researchers found that survey method based on collecting structured information about a current situation, in order to analyzing it, interpreting it, and identifying the reality of phenomenon is the most appropriate approach for achieving the purpose of study.

5.4 Study Population & Sample

The study society consists of all male and female teachers of science and physics, chemistry, Biology, and earth and environment sciences who teach during the second term of (2020-2021) school year, while the study sample consists of (446) male and female teachers, who have been selected using the simple random method, and table (1) shows occurrences and percentages of study sample according to the study variables (governorates, gender, course, teaching experience).

Table (1) frequencies and percentages of study sample according to study variables

Variables	Category	Frequency	%
Governorates	Amman	318	71.3
	Irbid	56	12.6
	Al-Karak	72	16.1
Gender	Male	124	27.8
	Female	322	72.2
Course	Biology	62	13.9
	Physics	44	9.9
	Chemistry	172	38.6
	Earth Sciences	68	15.2
	General Science	100	22.4
Experience	1-5 yrs.	102	22.9
	6-10 yrs.	140	31.4
	More than 10 yrs.	204	45.7
Total		446	100.0

5.5 Study Instruments /Supplement (1)

Researchers prepared the study tool to achieve the study purposes represented in revealing the barriers of using the flipped classroom strategy in science education, from the standpoint of science teachers in Amman, Irbid, and Al-Karak through the dialogue with a group of male and female teachers and through reviewing the

educational literature related to study topic, where researchers developed three fields for the tool (administrative and technological factors, teachers, and students).

5.5.1 Instrument Validity:

The study tool presented on six educational and English language arbitrators to express their opinions about the instrument, and modify, delete, or add any items they see appropriate.

5.5.2 Study Instrument Reliability:

To ensure the reliability of study tool, researchers used the Test-Retest method by implementing the scale and re-implementing it after two weeks on a group that consists of (30) participants from outside the study sample, and then calculated the Pearson Correlation Coefficient between their estimates at both times. Researchers also calculated the reliability coefficient using the internal consistency method and according to Cornbach Alpha equation. Table (2) shows the internal consistency coefficient according to Cornbach Alpha equation and the Retest reliability for the fields and overall degree, where values considered appropriate for the purposes of this study.

Table (2) internal consistency Cornbach Alpha & Retest reliability for fields and overall degree

Field	Re-Test Reliability	Cornbach Alpha
Teachers	0.91	0.82
Students	0.89	0.87
Administrative & Technological Factors	0.92	0.88
Overall Degree	0.91	0.90

5.6 Statistical Criterion & Scale:

Researchers adopted the Five Likert scale to answer the study tools, by giving each item on it one of five degrees (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree) which represent digitally (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) respectively, and used the following scale for results analysis:

1.00-2.33 Low 2.34-3.67 Medium 3.68-5.00 High

Researchers calculated the scale using the following equation:

(Higher scale limit (5) - Lower scale limit (1) / Number of categories required (3)

$(5-1)/3 = 1.33$, and then adding the answer (1.33) to the end of each category.

6. STUDY RESULTS & DISCUSSION

First Question: What are the barriers of using flipped classroom strategy from teachers' standpoint?

To answer this question, researchers calculated the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the barriers of flipped classroom, from teachers' standpoint, as shown in table (3) below:

Table (3) arithmetic means and standard deviations for the barriers of flipped classroom, from teachers' standpoint in a descending order according to means

Rank	Number	Field	Mean	STDEV	Level
1	2	Students	3.67	.648	Medium
2	3	Administrative & Technological Factors	3.49	.639	Medium
3	1	Teachers	3.33	.828	Medium
Overall Degree			3.50	.618	Medium

Table (3) shows that arithmetic means were between (3.33-3.67), with students ranked first with the highest mean of (3.67) and teachers came last with a mean of (3.33), while the mean for instrument as a whole amounted to (3.50), and to discuss results accurately, researchers calculated arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample members' estimates on the items of each field separately, and results were as follows:

First Field: Teachers

Table (4) arithmetic means and standard deviations for items related to teachers, in a descending order according to means

Rank	Number	Items	Mean	STDEV	Level
1	3	This method needs a lot of effort and time on my part	3.72	1.213	High
2	4	I find myself obliged re-teach the lesson traditionally after this method	3.52	1.068	Medium

3	1	This method is not appropriate for the scientific concepts I teach	3.44	1.205	Medium
4	8	This method reduces the importance of my role in teaching	3.35	1.216	Medium
5	2	Unavailability of opportunities to interact with my students	3.30	1.069	Medium
6	5	I don't prefer to follow up students through technology media	3.30	1.140	Medium
7	7	This method does not provide a creative environment	3.28	1.309	Medium
8	9	This method needs more than one teacher in the same time while teaching	3.18	1.238	Medium
9	10	This method needs special evaluation methods	3.16	1.237	Medium
10	6	I have a negative tendency towards education technology, even though I have master it	3.02	1.225	Medium
Teachers			3.33	0.828	Medium

Table (4) shows that arithmetic means were between (3.02-3.72), where the item (3) that states: "This method is not appropriate for the scientific concepts I teach" came in first place with a mean of (3.72), and item (4) which states: "I find myself obliged re-teach the lesson traditionally after this method" came in second place with a mean of (3.52), while the item (6) which states: "I have a negative tendency towards education technology, even though I have master it" came at last place with a mean of (3.02). The arithmetic mean of teachers' field as a whole amounted to (3.33) and this result may be attributed to the fact that teachers in government schools teach more than one classroom and for more than one division, therefore the use of strategy will require considerable time and effort, and this result agrees with the study of (Al-Lahibi & Reiss, 2021). In regard to re-teaching the lesson in the traditional way, teachers may be forced to do that due to the implementation method of this strategy, since the flipped classroom strategy is a response to calls for moving away from the traditional education and to go towards the self-learning, which requires the availability of diverse classroom environment that pushes students towards building and implementing the knowledge (Al-Healeh, 2016), and this linked to teachers' beliefs toward learning and education (Yahya, 2011), and also to their negative tendencies toward the use of technology which considers a key pillar of this strategy (Overmyer, 2011), as shown in the study results "I have a negative tendency towards education technology, even though I have master it", therefore the study does not agree with the study of (Abu Magnim, 2014; Ahmed, Sultan & Shaheen, 2017; Abbas 2020).

Second Field: Students

Table (5) arithmetic means and standard deviations for items related to students, in a descending order according to means

Rank	Number	Items	Mean	STDEV	Level
1	19	This method does not take into account the individual differences between students	4.09	0.786	High
2	14	This method suits a limited number of students	3.87	1.050	High
3	18	Frequent sitting in front of devices has negative effects on students	3.81	1.061	High
4	11	Students don't feel the serious of topic when following this method.	3.72	1.001	High
5	20	This method does not take into account the circumstances of students with special needs	3.71	1.146	High
6	15	This method does not assist students in self-learning	3.63	1.102	Medium
7	13	This method leads to lower motivation among students	3.51	1.153	Medium
8	16	Students do not have positive trends toward technology in learning and education	3.48	1.129	Medium
9	12	This method leads to the formation of alternative concepts among students	3.47	1.101	Medium
11	17	The absence of proper student enhancement using this way	3.44	1.136	Medium
Students			3.67	0.648	Medium

Table (5) shows that arithmetic means were between (3.44-4.09), where the item (19) that states: "This method does not take into account the individual differences between students" came in first place with a mean of (4.09), and item (14) which states: "This method suits a limited number of students" came in second place with a mean of (3.87), while the item (17) which states: "The absence of proper student enhancement using this way" came at last place with a mean of (3.44). The arithmetic mean of students' field as a whole amounted to (3.67) and this finding, from the standpoint of researchers is due to the fact that teachers did not employ the flipped classroom as proposed or as it should, considering that individual differences is a reason for the existence of this strategy where it allows students to interact with the subject as quickly as they want and as many times as they need through the technology used in this strategy represented in videos, where this result does not agree with the study's results of (Attaran & Zainuddin, 2016; Khalil, 2015; Johson, 2012).

Third Field: Administrative & Technological Factors

Table (5) arithmetic means and standard deviations for items related to administrative & technological factors, in a descending order according to means

Rank	Number	Items	Mean	STDEV	Level
1	24	The great teaching quorum stands in the way of implementing this method	3.83	1.224	High
2	27	Poor internet connectivity	3.70	1.063	High
3	23	I have not been subjected to specialized courses related to this method	3.58	1.134	High
4	21	I don't have technological means for this method	3.43	1.212	Medium
5	26	Lack of directing the educational supervisors toward this method	3.42	1.073	Medium
6	28	Lack of administrative coordination between elements of the educational process	3.39	1.179	Medium
7	25	There are no motivation from the management to use this method	3.30	1.171	Medium
8	22	I didn't undergo general technological courses	3.25	1.157	Medium
Administrative & Technological Factors			3.49	0.639	Medium

Table (6) shows that arithmetic means were between (3.25-3.83), where the item (24) that states: "The great teaching quorum stands in the way of implementing this method" came in first place with a mean of (3.83) and item (27) which states: "Poor internet connectivity" came in second place with a mean of (3.70), while the item (22) which states: "I didn't undergo general technological courses" came at last place with a mean of (3.25). The arithmetic mean of administrative & technological factors' field as a whole amounted to (3.49) and this finding is due to the fact that increased burden on teachers reduce their motivation, achievement, and keeping pace with the teaching strategies that require preparation and effort to provide a successful classroom environment (Hassan & Ahamed, 2016; Khalaf, 2013).

Second Question: Are there statistically significant differences in the barriers of using flipped classroom strategy, due to the difference in governorate, gender, educational Courses, and years of experience?

To answer this question, researchers calculated the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the barriers of flipped classroom according to governorate, gender, educational Courses, and years of experience variables, as shown in table (7) below :

Table (7) arithmetic means and standard deviations for the barriers of flipped classroom, according to governorate, gender, educational Courses, and years of experience variables

Variable	Categories	Mean	STDEV	Number
Governorate	Amman	3.42	0.594	318
	Irbid	3.66	0.455	56
	Al-Karak	3.70	0.757	72
Gender	Male	3.68	0.485	124
	Female	3.43	0.649	322
Educational Courses	Biology	3.44	0.780	62
	Physics	3.60	0.411	44
	Chemistry	3.51	0.602	172
	Earth Sciences	3.40	0.657	68
Years of Experience	General Science	3.53	0.581	100
	1-5 yrs.	3.57	0.666	102
	6-10 yrs.	3.55	0.630	140
	Greater than 10	3.43	0.579	204

Table (7) shows an apparent variation in the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the barriers of using flipped classroom, due to the different categories of governorate, gender, educational Courses, and years of experience variables and to indicate the significance of statistical differences between arithmetic means, researchers used the Two-Way Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) as shown in table (8) below:

Table (8) Analysis of MANOVA for the impact of governorate, gender, educational Courses, and years of experience on the barriers of using flipped classroom

Source of Variance	SS	DF	MS	F-value	Seg.
Governorate	8.482	2	4.241	12.072	0.000
Gender	2.686	1	2.686	7.645	0.006
Educational Courses	5.790	4	1.448	4.120	0.003
Years of Experience	1.217	2	0.609	1.732	0.178
Error	153.178	436	0.351		
Overall	169.986	445			

It shows from table (8) the following:

– The existence of statistically significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributable to the impact of governorate, where the F-value amounted to (12.072) with a statistical significant of (0.000) and to indicate the statistical significant multi differences between the arithmetic means, researchers used the Post Hoc Comparisons of Scheff'e Test Method, as shown in table (9)

Table (9) Post Hoc Comparisons of Scheff'e Method for the impact of governorate on barriers of using flipped classroom

		Mean	Amman	Irbid	Karak
Governorate	Amman	3.42			
	Irbid	3.66	0.24*		
	Karak	3.70	0.28*	0.04	

* Significant at the level ($\alpha=0.05$)

It shows from table (9) the existence of statistically significant differences ($\alpha=0.05$) between Amman on the one hand and Irbid and Karak both on the other hand, and differences came in favor of Irbid and Karak. This result may be attributed to the results of current study related to the poor internet connectivity compared with the capital of Amman.

– The existence of statistically significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributable to the impact of gender, where the F-value amounted to (7.645) with a statistical significant of (0.006) in favor of male. The result may be attributed to the extent female students committed at the female schools and their follow up on whatever they required to do more than male students' commitment.

– The nonexistence of statistically significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributable to the impact of experience, where the F-value amounted to (1.732) with a statistical significant of (0.178). This result may be attributed to the recent use of flipped classroom strategy at the Jordanian Ministry of Education.

– The existence of statistically significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributable to the impact of scientific Courses, where the F-value amounted to (4.120) with a statistical significant of (0.003) and to indicate the statistical significant multi differences between the arithmetic means, researchers used the Post Hoc Comparisons of Scheff'e Test Method, as shown in table (10) below:

Table (10) Post Hoc Comparisons of Scheff'e Method for the impact of scientific Courses on barriers of using flipped classroom

		Mean	Biology	Physics	Chemistry	Earth Sciences	General Sciences
Scientific Courses	Biology	3.44					
	Physics	3.60	0.16				
	Chemistry	3.51	0.07	0.09			
	Earth Sciences	3.40	0.04	0.20*			
	General Sciences	3.53	0.09	0.07	0.02		

* Significant at the level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table (10) shows statistically significant differences (0.05) between physics and earth sciences, and came in favor of physics. This finding according to the results of current study, may be attributed to the nature of

physical concepts as stated in "This method is not appropriate for the scientific concepts I teach", and "This method leads to the formation of alternative concepts among students".

7. RECOMMENDATION

Depend on study results, researchers made the following recommendation:

- The need to hold training workshops on flipped classroom strategy.
- Prepare help videos by groups of teachers to allow using it at several schools.
- Present practical implementation for using the flipped classroom strategy for male and female teachers via the Ministry of Education website.
- Conduct study on students' trends toward the flipped classroom strategy.

8. REFERENCES

- [1]Abanmi, F. (2016), "The impact of flipped classroom strategy on teaching interpretation of academic achievement and trends toward subjects among second grade secondary students", reading and knowledge magazine, issue (173)
- [2]Abbas, K. (2020), "Faculty's tendencies toward teaching with the flipped classroom strategy and their required training needs to use it", Faculty of Education Magazine, Kafir Al-Sheikh University, Faculty of Education, 20(2), 179-224
- [3]Abdul Lateef, S. (2016), "The impact of using flipped learning strategy on the development of cognitive aspects and creative thinking skills in the sports education course among female students of Sports Education Faculty, unpublished master thesis, Tanta University, Egypt
- [4]Abdul Wahid, A. (2015), "Flipped Classroom Strategy in Teaching Arabic for Non-Native Speakers, taking from the website <https://www.new-educ.com>, 15-07-2018
- [5]IbnMandour, M. (1414), "Lessan Al-Arabs", Dar Sader, Beirut, 267/7
- [6]Abu Magnim, K. (2014), "Middle-school sociology teachers' trends toward teaching by flipped classroom and their needs for training in order to use it", Journal of Arab Studies in Education and Psychology, 48(3), p. 150-205
- [7]Adedoja, G. (2016), "Pre-service teachers' challenges and attitude toward the flipped classroom", African Educational Research Journal, 4(1), 13-18
- [8]Ahmed, M., Sultan, M. &Shaheen, Y. (2017), Attitudes of teachers in the secondary education towards using flipped classroom strategy in science teaching: a field study in the city of Latakia, Tishreen University Journal for Research & Scientific Studies, 39(4), 563-581
- [9]Akwarshadeh, A. (2017), "The impact of using flipped learning strategy in the development of mathematical thinking and motivation towards learning mathematics among first scientific secondary school students", Unpublished master thesis, Al-Bayt University, Mafraq, Jordan
- [10]Alamry, A. (2017), "Flipped Learning and Self-Regulated Learning Experiences in Higher Education: A Qualitative Case Study", Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Western Sydney University, Sydney, Australia
- [11]Al-Ebikan, R. & Al-Hanaki, M. (2016), "The Impact of Teaching using Flipped Classroom Strategy on Motivation towards Middle School Learning", Specialized International Educational Journal, 5(8), p. 186-172
- [12]Al-Ghamedi, A. & Al-Atawi, A. (2018), "The Effectiveness of flipped classroom on the Achievement of Middle Third Graders to teach Computer & Information Technology course at Tabuk City", Reading and Knowledge Magazine, (202), 141-161
- [13]Al-Healeh, M. (2016), "The Design of Education; theory and practice", E6, Dar Al-Maseirah for publishing and distribution, Amman, Jordan
- [14]Al-Kuhaili, I. (2015), "The effectiveness of flipped classrooms in education", Dar Al-Zaman Library for publishing & distribution, Medina, KSA
- [15]Al-Laheibi, R. &Rayyes, I. (2020), "Trends of Faculty at Saudi Universities toward using the flipped learning and its implementation barriers in teaching", Jordanian journal of educational sciences, 16(3), 317-334
- [16]Al-Madan, F. (2015), "The Effect Of Blended Learning Approach On Fifth Grade Students' Academic Achievement In My Beautiful Language Textbook And The Development Of Their Verbal Creative Thinking In Saudi Arabia", Journal of International Education Research, 11(4), 253-260
- [17]Al-Mullah, A. (2007), "The obstacles that face educational scientific research and prevent the use of its results in the development of education and training", Arab Universities Union Magazine, N (49), Jordan
- [18]Al-Sawalha, A.; Al-Eyaddat, H. & Al-Hamleran, M. (2020), Impact of Flipped Learning Strategy on the development of motivation toward learning and educational achievement among Al-Huson University College students", Dirasat Journal: Educational Sciences, Vol. 47, 11, 405-420
- [19]Al-Shorman, A. (2015), "The Integrated Education & Flipped Learning", Dar Al-Massirah for publishing & distribution, Amman

- [20]Al-Talafha, H. &Ruwaili, F. (2020), “The impact of using flipped learning strategy on the development of self-organized learning skills among second middle school students in social and national studies at KSA”, *Journal of the Islamic University for Educational and Psychological Studies*, Vol. 28, No. 1, p. 617-646
- [21]Al-Zain, H. (2015), " The impact of using flipped learning strategy on the academic achievement of female students at education college in Princess NouraBint Abdul Rahman University”, *International Specialized Educational Journal*, 4 (1), p. 171-186
- [22]Ball, N. (2013), “Flipping the Classroom and Instructional Technology Integration in A college-level Information Systems Spreadsheet Course”, *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 61 (4), 580-563
- [23]Bergmann J. &Sams, A. (2012), “Flip your Classroom: Reach Every Student in Every Class Every Day”, Washington, DC, International Society for Technology in Education
- [24]Bruder, P. (2012), “The Flipped Classroom Reversing the Way we teach”, retrieved from: <http://www.njea.org/news-and-publications/njea-review/february-2012/the-flippedclassroomreversing-the-way-we-teach>. Access date 7-8-2018
- [25]Bergmann, J. &Sams, A. (2008), “Remixing chemistry class”, *Learning & Leading with Technology*, 36(4), 22-27, from:<https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ904290>
- [26]Bishop, J &Averleger, M. (2013), “The flipped classroom: A survey of the research 120th ASEE annual conference and exposition”, American Society for Engineering Education
- [27]Boettcher, J. & Conrad, R. (2010), “The online teaching Survival Guide”, San Francisco, Jossey-Bass, from: <https://www.mobt3ath.com/uplode/book/book-59307.pdf>
- [28]Brame, C. (2013), “Flipping the classroom”, Vanderbilt University for teaching, retrieved 5, 2018, from:<https://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/flipping-the-classroom/>
- [29]Butt, A. (2014), “Student views on the use of a flipped classroom approach: evidence from Australia”, *Business Education & Accreditation*, No (6), pp. 33–43
- [30]Eriebores (2013), “Niagara Falls High School Math Scores to 'FLIP' over”, Eric, retrieved 11, 2018, from:<http://www.e1b.org/WNYRIC.aspx?ArticleId=171>
- [31]Green, T. (2015), “Flipped classrooms: an agenda for innovative marketing education in the digital era”, *Marketing Education Review*, 25(3), pp. 179–191
- [32]Halili, H. &Zainuddin, Z. (2016), “Flipped Classroom Research & Trends from Different Fields of Study”, *International Review of Research in Open & Distributed Learning*, 17(3),313-340,retrieved on 10, 2018, from:<http://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/2274/3699>
- [33]Hamdan, N.; McKnight, P.; McKnight, K. &Arfstrom, K. (2013), “A White Paper Based on the Literature Review Titled: A Review of Flipped Learning”, *Flipped Learning*
- [34]Hassan I. O. &Ahamed H. H. (2016), “The Impact of Instructional Technologies in Teaching English in Sudanese Secondary Schools in Khartoum State”, *International Journal of English Language Teaching*, 4 (1), 56-63
- [35]Herreid, C & Schiller, N. (2013), “Case Studies and the flipped classroom”, *Journal ofCollege Science Teaching*, National Science Teachers Association, p.p62from:<http://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/2274/3699>
- [36]Karabenick, S. A. & Conley, A. (2011), “Teacher Motivation for Professional Development”, *Ann Arbor*
- [37]Khalil, I. (2015), “The impact of using flipped classroom strategy on the development of some self-organized learning components and trends toward subject among sixth-graders”, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304270120>
- [38]Milheim, W. (2006), “Strategies for the Design and Delivery of Blended Learning Courses”, *Journal of Educational Technology*, 18(3), 99-105
- [39]Overmyer, G. R. (2014), “The flipped Classroom Model for College Algebra: Effects on Students Achievement”, Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, USA
- [40]Raja, T. (2013), “Flipped classroom concept application”, *The Business and Management Review*, 3(4), pp. 213-234
- [41]Sprenger, M. (2010), “Brain-Based teaching in the digital age”, Alexandria ASCD, from: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED512513>
- [42]Zainuddin, Z. &Halili, S. (2016), “Flipped classroom research and trends from different fields of study”, *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 17(3), pp. 313–340

Author Information

Shaimaa' Mkhymryahya

Assistant Professor of Curriculum and Instruction Al Balqa Applied University/ Department Science of Education, Irbid University College.

Mohammad Nayef Ayasrah

Associate Professor of Special Education (Talent and Creativity), Al Balqa Applied University/ Department Science of Education, Irbid University College

Mohareb Ali Alsmadi

Associate Professor of Curriculum and Instruction Al Balqa Applied University/ Department Science of Education, Ajloun University College.

Shorouq Mansour al-etan

A Teacher At The Ministry Of Education In Jordan
